

Effect of Structure on Surfaceance of Sodium Salts of *N*-Acylamino Acids in Aqueous Solutions

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Physical properties and performance characteristics of sodium salts of several *tlc*-pure *N*-acyl amino acids made from *glc*-pure even chain fatty acids from capric through stearic are reported. The effect of acyl chain length and the differences in the structure of constituent amino acid of seven homologous series of amide intermediate linked carboxylate surfactants of this class on the properties are discussed.

IN an earlier communication¹, preparation of several pure *N*-acyl amino acids and peptides, and the effect of structure on their melting behaviour were reported and discussed. The properties of aqueous solutions of sodium salts of the *N*-acyl amino acids (prepared earlier¹) from even chain fatty acids are now being communicated.

Experimental

Preparation and purification of surfactants: The *tlc*-pure *N*-acyl amino acids from *glc*-pure even chain fatty acids from capric through stearic and seven different amino acids (whose preparation and properties were reported), *viz.* glycine (gly) DL-alanine (ala), sarcosine (sar), DL-valine (val), L-leucine (leu), L-aspartic (asp) and L-lysine (lys) were used as raw material. These were taken in 95% ethanol (10% w/v), warmed to 60°, and neutralised with ethanolic NaOH solution to the exact end-point, allowed to cool to room tempera-

ture and filtered. The crystallised surfactants were washed with acetone and finally dried at 60° under reduced pressure (10 mm Hg). The yield of the first crop of crystals varied from 80-90%. In case of valinates and leucinates, due to the difficulties encountered during the crystallisation, absolute alcohol was used in place of 95% ethanol.

Properties of aqueous solutions of surfactants:

The data relating to solubility and hydrolysis in water are given in Table 1. The solubility is adjudged by cloud point (c. p.) (not given) and Krafft point (K.p.)². The minimum amount of Ca⁺⁺ ions (expressed as ppm CaCO₃) needed to make 0.5% surfactant solution to attain a defined turbidity was determined according to the modified Hart method³ (Table 1). pH of salt solutions of different concentrations in distilled water at 30° were determined using a digital pH meter having an accuracy of ±0.01 unit. From the

TABLE 1—BULK PROPERTIES OF SODIUM SALTS OF *N*-ACYL AMINO ACIDS

Acyl chain A. acid	K.P. ^a (°C)					Maximum hydrolysis ^b (% at 30°)				
	10	12	14	16	18	10	12	14	16	18
gly	+	36	47	55	66	4.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.6 × 10 ⁻³	6.9 × 10 ⁻³	1.69	6.46
	(40)	(65)	(93)	(-)	(-)	(1.30)	(0.75)	(0.10)	(0.05)	(0.05)
DL-ala	+	18	32	45	56	3.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	3.0 × 10 ⁻³	4.8 × 10 ⁻³	0.35
	(154)	(666)	(323)	(301)	(-)	(1.40)	(0.75)	(0.29)	(0.075)	(0.075)
sar	+	+	+	2	(33)	3.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.2 × 10 ⁻³	2.4 × 10 ⁻³	4.4 × 10 ⁻³	8.0 × 10 ⁻³
	(109)	(258)	(273)	(229)	(229)	(1.40)	(0.75)	(0.40)	(0.12)	(0.10)
DL-val	+	+	+	8	36	7.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.9 × 10 ⁻³	4.5 × 10 ⁻³	8.4 × 10 ⁻³	1.45
	(109)	(372)	(400)	(330)	(229)	(1.50)	(0.50)	(0.10)	(0.05)	(0.01)
L-leu	+	+	+	+	46	3.1 × 10 ⁻³	1.3 × 10 ⁻³	5.1 × 10 ⁻³	9.0 × 10 ⁻³	5.3
	(94)	(229)	(243)	(236)	(-)	(1.30)	(0.40)	(0.10)	(0.075)	(0.075)
L-asp	+	+	+	+	46	1.9 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.3 × 10 ⁻³	2.8 × 10 ⁻³	4.4 × 10 ⁻³	0.62
	(47)	(78)	(109)	(169)	(154)	(1.0)	(1.52)	(0.10)	(0.05)	(0.05)
L-lys	8	34	61	84		1.14				
	(184)	(229)	(-)	(-)		(0.01)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)

^aFigures in parenthesis are Ca⁺⁺ ion tolerance in ppm CaCO₃. ^bFigures in brackets are concns. (%) at which the max. hydrolysis occurs.

(+) = Solutions clear at 0°, (-) = Solutions hazy under test conditions.

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data, the extent of hydrolysis was calculated at each concentration; the extent of observed maximum hydrolysis and concentrations at which these occur are reported in Table 1.

Surface tension (S.T.) of the surfactant solutions at various concentrations and at 30, 40 and 60° were determined by capillary rise method⁴, but only the observed minimum steady S.T. values attained at 60° are given in Table 2. From the graph of S.T. at 30° against surfactant concentration in each case, the molar concentration (C) needed to reduce S.T. of water by 20 units were read, and the values of $-\log C$ (termed⁵ as pC_{20}) were plotted against the number of carbon atoms in the acyl chain of surfactants (Fig. 1). Critical

Fig. 1. Relationship of pC_{20} vs number of carbon atoms in acyl chain of sodium salts of *N*-acyl amino acids.

micelle concentration (C.M.C.) obtained by the pinacyanol chloride-dye method⁶ at 30° are given in Table 2. The values obtained by this dye method agreed very closely with the values obtained from S.T. data (the concentration at the point of interception of two straight lines obtained in the plot of S.T. against log concentration) and from conductivity data (the concentration at the point

of inflection in the plot of specific conductance against concentration). The C.M.C. value obtained by the latter two methods hence, are not given. The relationship of log molar C.M.C. obtained by conductance method at 30° against the number of carbon atoms in acyl chains of different series is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Relationship of log molar C.M.C. and number of carbon atoms in acyl chain of sodium salts of *N*-acyl amino acids.

Table 3 gives data on wetting power of 0.1% surfactant solutions at 60° by the canvas disc method⁷ and emulsifying power⁸ for liquid paraffin-water system as represented by the time needed for separation of a known volume (20 ml) of aqueous phase at 60° from emulsions made under identical conditions while using 0.1% surfactant solutions. By the procedure given by Borghetty and Bergman⁹, the lime soap dispersing (L.S.D.) numbers were determined for all the surfactants (data not given). Foaming ability (Table 4) of 0.25 and 0.05% solutions, at 60° were determined by the Ross and Miles pour test method in a locally

TABLE 2- SURFACTANT PROPERTIES OF SODIUM SALTS OF *N*-ACYL AMINO ACIDS

Acyl chain A. acid	Minimum S.T. (dynes cm ⁻¹ at 60°)					C.M.C. (mmol dm ⁻³ at 30°)				
	10	12	14	16	18	10	12	14	16	18
gly	34.5	35.8	35.6	35.4	36.1	45.72	14.66	4.30	1.25	0.44
DL-ala	33.8	34.5	34.7	34.3	35.0	38.60	11.53	3.80	1.23	0.40
sar	33.8	34.0	34.2	34.2	34.1	53.08	14.57	3.99	1.12	0.32
DL-val	30.0	31.0	33.3	32.1	32.4	32.22	9.97	3.24	0.82	0.25
L-leu	28.6	29.0	30.0	30.3	29.9	19.09	6.09	2.04	0.67	0.22
L-asp	39.6	39.3	40.1	40.6	40.8	112.20	33.56	13.02	3.69	1.33
L-lys	21.7	23.8	22.5	23.6	-	1.74	0.90	0.27	0.17	-

fabricated unit as per specifications¹⁰. Detergency was tested by the gain in reflectance (ΔR) obtained by washing soiled cloth in a Terg-O-Tometer (U.S. Testing Company) under uniform conditions⁸. The data obtained while washing the soiled cotton cloth in distilled water at 60° using 0.25% pure surfactant solution and also 0.25% surfactant having 0.025% sodium metasilicate are given in Table 4.

Results and Discussion

Effect of increasing acyl chain length in the homologous surfactants: The solubility of surfactant decreases (increase in K.p. and c.p.) as the acyl chain length increases in a homologous series (Table 1). Maximum Ca⁺⁺ ion tolerance is exhibited by a middle member of a homologous series; lauroyl derivative in the lysinate series, palmitoyl in aspartate series and myristoyl in the rest have highest Ca⁺⁺ ion tolerance amongst surfactants of the respective series. It is of interest to note that Ca⁺⁺ ion tolerance is high for the lowermost homologue whose C.M.C. is below 0.5% (at which concentration the test is done) while those with C.M.C. greater than 0.5% (as for the C₁₀ fatty acids) have poor tolerance to Ca⁺⁺ ion.

pH of the solutions (not given) at all the concentrations tested increase with increase in acyl chain length in a given series, like for normal carboxylates. pH of 0.1% solutions are 7.1±0.1 for all the lauroyl derivatives excluding the diacylated lysinates (8.8), while the stearyl derivatives have pH between 8.33 to 10.23 depending on the amino acid in the surfactant. The effect of increasing acyl chain length on the increase in the maximum percentage hydrolysis is clearly seen from the data given in Table 1; the higher homologue in a series undergoes hydrolysis to a greater extent, but the concentration at which this occurs is lower or equal in a few cases for immediate higher homologue in a surfactant series.

The S.T. of surfactant solutions decreases as the concentration is increased and reaches a steady value at higher concentrations; the minimum S.T. values occur at and around the respective C.M.C. of a surfactant. In general, the minimum values obtained are lowest for caprio acid derivatives, and they increase as the series ascend, though not significantly. The effect of increasing acyl chain length on the ability to lower S.T. can be seen from Fig. 1. The pC₂₀ values progressively and linearly increase as the series ascend. For the

TABLE 3—WETTING AND EMULSIFYING POWER OF SURFACTANTS AT 60°

Acyl chain A. acid	Wetting time (sec)					Time (sec) for separation of 20 ml of aqueous phase from emulsion				
	10	12	14	16	18	10	12	14	16	18
gly	> 600	29.8	65.5	151.0	330.0	+	+	+	182	484
DL-ala	> 600	6.4	7.0	10.4	20.0	+	153	234	241	337
sar	> 600	19.4	4.4	8.9	17.1	+	120	278	278	244
DL-val	> 600	3.5	6.0	12.1	27.3	+	300	291	288	375
L-leu	17.8	3.6	9.1	24.0	56.3	+	271	383	482	623
L-asp	> 600	113.0	110.0	114.0	120.0	+	+	+	+	246
L-lys	< 1.0	30.2	293.0	600	-	219	209	791	90	

(+) - Aqueous and oil phase start separating immediately.

TABLE 4—FOAMING AND DETERGENT POWER OF SURFACTANTS AT 60°

Acyl chain A. acid	Ross-Miles foam height (mm for 0.25 % solutions)*					Grain in reflectance of soiled cloth after washing (ΔR with 0.25% solution)**				
	10	12	14	16	18	10	12	14	16	18
gly	7	107	206	230	170	4.7	7.2	19.7	19.9	23.5
DL-ala	(0)	(0)	(44)	(225)	(162)	(10)	(22.9)	(25.9)	(26.8)	(28.3)
sar	13	149	188	200	183	3.2	6.3	19.8	20.1	22.9
DL-val	(0)	(11)	(100)	(196)	(180)	(9.2)	(21.8)	(24.6)	(24.8)	(26.1)
L-leu	15	145	176	186	185	3.5	7.1	14.2	18.1	14.4
L-asp	(7)	(10)	(110)	(150)	(176)	(13.3)	(21.0)	(25.6)	(27.8)	(25.3)
L-lys	14	175	186	180	165	2.7	12.6	18.7	18.8	20.5
DL-val	(0)	(23)	(182)	(175)	(155)	(9.8)	(21.3)	(23.0)	(23.0)	(23.7)
L-leu	25	180	174	179	165	3.0	12.7	15.0	16.9	18.6
L-asp	(7)	(65)	(173)	(162)	(163)	(13.8)	(22.3)	(23.2)	(23.3)	(23.0)
L-lys	0	110	145	185	220	3.4	3.5	4.3	18.7	25.1
DL-ala	(0)	(15)	(25)	(25)	(145)	(9.6)	(10.5)	(11.4)	(26.2)	(32.1)
sar	195	163	45	0	-	8.0	10.6	21.0	12.5	-
DL-val	(185)	(150)	(42)	(0)	-	(23.2)	(23.3)	(27.1)	(20.3)	-

* Values in parenthesis, for 0.05% solution. ** Values in parenthesis, when 0.025% sodium metasilicate added to surfactant solution.

glycinate, alaninate, valinate and leucinate, pC_{20} increases by 0.44 units for every addition of ethylene group in acyl chain indicating that a surface concentration close to saturation value is obtained for the higher homologue with 35% of the bulk phase concentration required for the lower. In sarcosinates, the respective values are 0.54 and 30%, respectively.

C.M.C. values when plotted against number of carbon atoms in acyl chain of surfactants, give straight line relationships (Fig. 2), but the slopes differ for different series indicating the influence of constituent amino acid in the compound on the surfactant properties of these, as for pC_{20} values. The slopes vary from 0.24 to 0.26 and are lower than that of soaps (0.29 to 0.30); the lower values indicate incomplete transfer of molecules out of the aqueous environment and may imply greater penetration of water into the micelle of these compounds because of the intermediate polar-amide linkage in this class of surfactants.

These compounds, in general, are poor lime soap dispersing agents and have L.S.D. numbers over 40 (data not given) while the L.S.D. numbers of commonly used agents for this purpose are below 5. The lauroyl derivatives of glycinate, alaninate, valinate, leucinate, sarcosinate, aspartate and lysinate have L.S.D. numbers > 100, 40, 48, 72, 80, > 100 and 60, respectively. The L.S.D. numbers are minimum at an optimum chain length as was found for Ca^{++} ion tolerance; either lauroyl or myristoyl derivative are best as compared to higher and lower homologues of their respective series.

Similarly, in the ability to wet the canvas disc at 60° (Table 3) either lauroyl or myristoyl derivatives are best in their respective series except in the case of diacylated lysines where instantaneous wetting takes place for capric derivatives (sinking time < 1 sec) while the higher ones are not so good.

The emulsifying ability, on the other hand, increases with increasing acyl chain length in all the cases (Table 3), excluding palmitoyl lysinate. Even though only the time needed for separation of 20 ml of aqueous phase from paraffin oil-water emulsion prepared under similar conditions are given in Table 3, the trend is the same for the separation of 15, 10 and 5 ml aqueous phase from emulsions, but the difference in separation times between any two surfactants progressively get diminished in the three cases.

Except for lysinates which are diacyl derivatives for which the lower derivatives give better foam, increasing acyl chain length increases the foaming ability at 60° upto certain length and further increase results in decreased foam heights (Table 4). The stability of foam formed (data not given) is at par with foaming ability. The observed trend is similar at lower concentration of 0.05% (Table 4) except that foam build-up is extremely poor for the lower

homologues (whose C.M.C. is very much higher than 0.05%) and slightly poorer for the higher (myristoyl and above).

The deterative power of surfactants increased with increasing chain length and the lower homologues are inferior except in the case of lysinates where dimyristoyl derivative was found to be the best. Presence of 10% metasilicate improved the detergency in all the cases (Table 4), but the building action is higher for those surfactants which are originally poor.

In a homologues series, for higher homologues, the concentrations at which the performance test is conducted are higher than their respective C.M.C. while they are lower than the C.M.C. for the lower. Hence, the observed effects of optimum chain length could be attributed jointly to the H.L.B. of the surfactants as well as the proximity of concentration of surfactants to their respective C.M.C. values, apart from the differences in their tendency to hydrolyse in water at a given concentration. It is of interest to note that the magnitude of changes in properties and performance characteristics by increasing acyl chain length by two methylene groups differs from series to series indicating also the influence of constituent amino acids on properties.

Effect of variation in structure of constituent amino acid of surfactants: Compared to their corresponding sodium salts of fatty acids¹¹, the sodium salts of *N*-acyl amino acids are more soluble except the diacylated lysinates, in distilled water and can tolerate Ca^{++} ion to some extent; they hydrolyse less in water and have lower C.M.C. Perhaps because of the amide intermediate linkages between the carboxylate group and the hydrophobic long acyl chain and the type of substituent groups in the constituent amino acids on H.L.B., the performance characteristics as surfactants is improved in some, while in others they are adversely affected and their influence vary depending on acyl chain length.

Sodium salts of *N*-acyl amino acids are, in general, more soluble than their corresponding soaps because of the presence of intermediate amide linkage in the former which being polar contributes to greater hydration. Among themselves, the glycinate are less soluble than the others except the diacyl lysinates. The presence of substituent alkyl group in the α -position of the simplest amino acid glycine decreases the K.p. sharply despite increase in molecular weight, and the decrease depends on the bulkiness of the substituent group (Table 1). Shift of the alkyl group from the α -position (in alaninate) to the nitrogen atom (in sarcosinate) significantly decreases the K.p. Substitution of H atom with an alkyl group near the amide linkage or on the N atom increases solubility over glycinate because of the weaker intermolecular hydrogen

bonding at the amide linkage in the former. This, and hydration seem to be the predominant forces which determine the solubility of these surfactants in water. The aspartates, having a CH_2COONa group in the α -position, have higher solubility because of two polar carboxylate groups; the diacylates of lysine because of bulkiness have higher K.p. and c.p. compared to all the corresponding monoacylates. Apart from the lower solubility, the difference between K.p. and c.p. (not given) for the diacylates is about 21° , which is higher than the observed difference of 7 to 14° for the other surfactants. The average differences between the K.p. of adjacent homologues for the glycine, alanine, valine and leucine series are about 10 , 13 , 28 and 46° , respectively (Table 1). The differences increase as the size of the substituent group on the carbon atom increases, and also when the methyl group is shifted from the α -position (alaninates, 13°) to nitrogen atom (sarcosinates, 31°). It was observed that the solubility of some of the compounds in soft water (100 ppm CaCO_3) is somewhat anomalous. Lauroyl, myristoyl, palmitoyl and stearoyl derivatives of valine and leucine at concentrations of 0.05, 0.1 and/or 0.25% were soluble at room temperature in soft water, but became turbid on heating; on cooling back to room temperature, the solutions became clear after a period of 1 to 2 h. This confirms that the higher solubility of *N*-acyl amino acid salts over the corresponding soaps is due predominantly to the hydration of the amide linkage rather than ionisation of the carboxyl group enhanced by the presence of the alkyl group in the α -position.

For a given acyl chain, the extent of hydrolysis occurring for different amino acid derivatives differ. Substituent groups, such as methyl or isopropyl at the α -carbon atom or methyl group on nitrogen of the amino acid (as in alanine, valine and sarcosine, respectively) increase the strength of the acid (lower hydrolysis) as compared to the simple glycines. Presence of additional CH_2 group in valinates (as for leucinates) increases hydrolysis, and is similar to the observation made when increasing the acyl chain. Comparing the glycines and soaps having same acyl chain, the former are stronger acids in spite of having an additional CH_2 group. Thus, *N*-lauroyl glycinate hydrolyses to a lesser extent than sodium laurate (maximum % hydrolysis 5.6×10^{-3} and 7.2×10^{-2} , respectively), and myristoyl glycinate (6.9×10^{-2}) lesser than sodium myristate (8.7×10^{-1}). Amongst all the derivatives, the diacyl derivatives (lysines) hydrolyse to the greatest extent while for the dicarboxylates (aspartates) it is the least. Thus, it is seen that addition of a CH_2/CH_3 group in the acyl chain of surfactant increases hydrolysis, the same when added to the α -carbon atom of amino acid part decreases hydrolysis. The minimum S.T. values are lower when a larger hydrocarbon substituent group is present. Thus, for a given acyl chain the leucinates, valinates, alaninates and

glycinates in that order (Table 2) give lower minimum S.T. values. While the diacyl lysine derivatives give the lowest minimum S.T. values, and the dicarboxylate (aspartates) have the highest.

The presence of small hydrocarbon group, such as methyl, isopropyl and isobutyl on the α -carbon atom of glycine leads to a decrease in C.M.C., showing that they contribute to hydrophobicity of the molecule. However, they are equivalent to only 0.3, 0.8 and 1.3 CH_2 groups in the acyl chain length, respectively (concluded by extrapolation of lines in Fig. 2). In aspartates, the CH_2COONa group gives rise to a higher C.M.C. due to the increase in the free energy of the system brought about by bringing two highly polar carboxylate groups of a molecule together in the micelle; this has a disrupting effect on micelle formation due to Coulombic repulsive forces.

The performance characteristics of the surfactants are influenced by the structure of the amino acid present, but the magnitude of influence differs depending on the acyl chain length of the surfactants as seen from Tables 3 and 4.

In wetting power, dicaproyl lysinate is the best, and dimyristoyl lysinate is the best emulsifying agent amongst all the compounds studied. The aspartates, which are dicarboxylates, are poor wetting and emulsifying agents (the stearoyl being better than glycines). The effect of α -H substitution of glycines with small alkyl group is to improve the wetting and emulsifying powers. Taking the myristoyl derivatives as an example, it can be seen that lysinate is the best emulsifying and detergent agent but has poor wetting and foaming powers. In all the four performance properties, myristoyl aspartate which is a dicarboxylate surfactant, is the poorest perhaps because of H.L.B. considerations. Substitution at the α -carbon atom improves wetting and emulsifying powers but decreases foaming power. Detergency is also affected marginally. The extent of the influence depends on the molecular weight of the substituent group in the α -position. The emulsifying power progressively increases as the bulk of molecule increases but foaming and detergent power progressively decrease as seen by comparing the data of the respective alaninates, valinates and leucinates.

The substituted amino acid derivatives have in general a better wetting power compared to glycines, but if the substituent becomes too big as in leucinates, it is again adversely affected (though still better than glycines). This clearly shows the influence of substituent groups on the performance of these surfactants, and is confirmed by the fact that caproyl leucinate is the best wetting agent amongst all the monoacylated derivatives from capric acid. However, as the acyl chain is ascended or descended, some variations are seen from the observations perhaps because the acyl chain of surfactant also has influence on H.L.B.

TABLE 5—C.M.C. AND PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF STRUCTURALLY DIFFERING PAIRS HAVING SAME MOLECULAR WEIGHT (SUMMARISED FROM TABLES 3 AND 4)

Surfactant	C.M.C. at 30° mmol dm ⁻³	Wetting time sec	Time for separation of 20 ml aqueous phase sec	Foam height mm	Detergency of 0.25% solutions (ΔR)*
Caproyl leu	19.09	17.8	+	25	3.0 (13.8)
Myristoyl gly	4.30	65.5	+	206	19.7 (25.9)
Lauroyl leu	6.09	3.6	271	180	12.7 (22.3)
Palmitoyl gly	1.25	151.0	182	230	19.9 (26.8)
Myristoyl leu	2.04	9.1	383	174	15.0 (23.2)
Stearoyl gly	0.44	330.0	484	170	23.5 (28.3)
Myristoyl val	3.24	6.0	291	186	18.7 (23.0)
Palmitoyl ala	1.23	10.4	241	200	20.1 (24.8)
Palmitoyl val	0.82	12.1	288	180	18.8 (23.0)
Stearoyl ala	0.40	20.0	337	183	22.9 (26.1)

* Values in parenthesis, ΔR values when 0.025% sodium metasilicate is added to surfactant solution.

Alaninates and sarcosinates which are respectively α -methyl and *N*-methyl glycinates, differ in properties. The presence of methyl group on nitrogen improves emulsifying and wetting power while decreases foaming and deterative powers for all the fatty acid derivatives above myristoyl derivatives.

While considering leucinates and glycinates having same molecular weight, (e.g. lauroyl leucinate and palmitoyl glycinate) the substitution of α -hydrogen of glycinates with bulkier isobutyl group as in leucinates, results in increased C.M.C., improved wetting and emulsifying powers, but poorer foaming and deterative powers. Similar conclusions can be drawn while comparing valinates and alaninates having the same molecular weight. For example, amongst myristoyl valinate and palmitoyl alaninate (valinate having a bulkier isopropyl group compared to the methyl in alaninates) the former has higher C.M.C., better wetting and emulsifying power but poorer foaming and deterative powers. These influences can clearly be seen from the data summarised in Table 5.

It may be concluded that the properties and physical characteristics of *N*-acyl amino acid salts

are collectively influenced by the acyl chain length, intermediate amide linkage and substituent group present in glycine molecule.

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